

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES
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ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-Creation Integrated Methodology- final version

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this deliverable is to document the unified methodology employed in ToyLabs as it has been updated since the first (D2.1) version, as a result of the experience gained by further research, the implementation of the ToyLabs platform and its components and feedback gained from the pilot partners during this process. This methodology is to be used by the toy industry, and specifically SMEs, for attaching more value to their design processes and new product development activities. This will be achieved through the collaboration of different stakeholders, building on the notion of co-creation and open innovation that aims at accelerating their innovation cycles resulting to more inspirational, novel and desirable creations, while also partner matching functionalities will make possible to find time-wisely and effortlessly the right partner for the task in question, augmented reality will ensure the acquisition of informed and accurate end-users’ feedback and finally market trend analysis will integrate crowd wisdom into new product development activities for the toy industry. In an effort to extend the usefulness of this methodology, more stakeholders have been directly involved in the platform with various responsibilities.

In this context, the landscape analysis implemented in D2.1 is updated in section 2 of this deliverable on the research fields of “Co-creation and Open Innovation”, “Market Trend Analysis”, “Augmented Reality for feedback gathering” and finally “Partner Matching”, both from the perspective of the manufacturing industry in general but also zooming in the toy industry, in particular, to identify its state-of-the-art with respect to the general research community. This analysis evinced the variety and volume of ongoing research studies on these fields, but also the challenge to be met inside ToyLabs to turn these results towards the needs of the toy industry, thus providing a unique offering.

The insights gained from the expansion of this literature review were used as input for the update of the ToyLabs methodological approach for renovating the design and manufacturing processes of the toy industry. In more detail, the discrete methodological steps of the holistic ToyLabs methodology under the spirit of Open Innovation are presented, while afterwards the discrete methodological foundations for market trend analysis, augmented reality for feedback gathering and partner matching are shown. The results of the initial workflow created in D2.1 was used to guide the next steps of the project and specifically the design and development of the ToyLabs platform and its added-value components.

The work done on this deliverable showcases this updated methodology, while pinpointing the changes made during this iteration.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

To redesign the way that the toy industry approaches new product development through ToyLabs, a complete, well-defined and extendable methodology needs to be defined. In that view, the central questions that are to be answered, in the context of the present deliverable, have to do with “What will ToyLabs do?” and “Why is it going to do it?”. This deliverable aims to show a coherent and easily understandable methodology and blueprint of how the various project’s goals as identified by its stakeholders’ requirements, the previous version of the methodology, the implementation of the ToyLabs platform, and the feedback gained from the pilot partners, while showing how some of the top level technical aspects of the project are being implemented. The contents of the following chapters provide the material that was encoded into technical specifications for WP3, which fed the implementation in WP3 and WP4, and then returned to provide this update through a continuous feedback loop.

This document aims to strike a balance between the amount of in-depth analysis necessary to feed the technical requirements of the platform, and the descriptiveness needed to make its contents accessible to all other stakeholders, toy manufacturers and FabLabs, ready to accept their input, and become the basis of their understanding and continuous interaction with the ToyLabs community. In this spirit, the ToyLabs methodology is described in steps, under the umbrella of Open Innovation, thus forming the methodological foundations, which will be able to be treated as stand-alone methodologies and to develop a workflow that merges these foundations into a holistic approach.

Based on the DoA of the ToyLabs project, this deliverable is titled “ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation Integrated Methodology-final version” and is the direct outcome of all WP2 tasks until month 13 of the project. This document is the second and final version, incorporating all further research and further feedback from other work packages into the methodology of ToyLabs until that point.

1.2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The methodological approach by which the current deliverable takes form starts from a general perspective and focuses on defining an illustrative methodology for each of the ToyLabs main components. In the first part, the core conclusions from the Landscape Analysis are presented, starting with a study of the state-of-play on ToyLabs domains of interest, as well as the existing practices on these domains concerning the toy industry, and a classification of these domains into broader

categories and fields of study. These fields are specifically chosen to be leveraged as input for the clarification of the ToyLabs methodological foundations, as described in the DoA, representing distinct tasks within the project. In the second part of the analysis, these are matched to the resulting methodology, which is again separated in these components, starting with a recording of the stakeholders of the ToyLabs solution. In this version of the methodology, the Landscape analysis focuses more on some specific domains tackled by the methodology, namely feedback management in collaborative environments, and social network analysis, where blogs and social media are handled differently, while capturing emotion rather than just sentiment is targeted. At the same time, the partner matching analysis is updated to take more business interoperability issues into account.

Specifically, the first part deals with Open Innovation and Co-creation models from both the traditional manufactures’ perspective and then from the side of the toy industry, combined with the current academic literature on the subject. From it, the Open Innovation and Co-Creation Holistic Methodology is formed. The aim of the task is to use the existing experience to find how traditional companies in the toy industry can embrace an open innovation ecosystem, by supporting them in the process, according to their specific needs. In this version, specific aspects of the feedback by retailers are taken into account, where the addition of this stakeholder as an active user of the platform and the ToyLabs holistic approach, allows for a more in-depth understanding of the performance of a new toy in the market, valuable insights into design features and issues, and new or updated toy ideas.

The second part deals with Market Trend and Social Feedback analysis. To capture the landscape in this area, both the specific state-of-the-art practices to extract market trends in the toy industry are documented, as well the current state of the field of Social Network Analysis for trends detection and feedback management. These are combined in the following chapter to form the Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis methodology, answering the question of how the Social Web can be incorporated indirectly into new product development processes, serving as useful information source to capture underlying trends in toy industry’s specific domains (e.g. dolls, puzzles etc.) as well as the sentiment of the social media users talking about these topics. In this version, a specific differentiation between the two workflows, namely Market Trends and Social Feedback is made, while more details and in-depth analysis is made for each.

The third part refers to the use of Augmented Reality (AR) for end-user feedback collection. The current academic literature and commercial approaches are initially documented and considered in order to derive the optimal methodology to introduce the use of Mixed and Augmented Reality to gather end-user feedback, taking into consideration the particularities of the toy industry, and especially the considerations applicable to the SME toy manufacturers. In this version of the methodology, technologies and tools introduced during 2017 that were not included in the first

release were considered in the landscape analysis, including information about ARKit which was selected. Furthermore, the methodology was expanded to include details about the provisioning of fully anonymised feedback and a workflow of the operation of the ToyLabs AR mobile app has been added.

Lastly, the fourth part refers to the partner matching and selection methodology, starting from documenting the methods that are currently employed in the industry to find and select partners and sub-contractors, the range of criteria and priorities used to do so, and transitioning to the description of the Partner Matching and Selection Methodology for ToyLabs as well as the reasoning behind it. In this version of the methodology, the notion of a reputation factor for partners is introduced, a more flexible selection of partner matching criteria is described, where the user isn't restricted to the ones identified in the Blueprint Model, and based on more involved security and authentication mechanism, a graded access approach is presented, allowing the disclosure of information based on specific needs and functional roles within the system.

Figure 1-1 Deliverable Methodology Outline

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The structure of the document is as follows:

Chapter 1 introduces this document, in which the purpose and scope of the deliverable at hand, the methodological approach of the research done to achieve this result, its current structure, the relation of this deliverable and its tasks to other work packages and tasks.

Chapter 2 is the Landscape Analysis performed to create the ToyLabs methodology. It starts with the identification of the ToyLabs domains of interest that

will be examined in the following subsections as part of this chapter and continues with four main scientific fields, that of Co-creation and Open Innovation, Market Trend Analysis, Augmented Reality for feedback gathering and Partner Matching, that are being researched both from a more general perspective as well as zooming in the toy industry if relevant, remarkable work or application examples can be found there for each of the above mentioned domains.

Chapter 3 contains the methodological foundations on which the ToyLabs project and platform are based. It starts with the identification of the key stakeholders and then it defines the methodology, as a matter of discrete and successive steps, starting with the ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation methodology, the Market Trends and Social Feedback methodology, End-User Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality methodology and finally the ToyLabs methodology for Partner Matching.

Chapter 4 documents the main conclusions of the deliverable at hand, as well as a brief report on the next steps to be taken in the project with respect to WP2 activities.

1.4 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPS AND TASKS

This deliverable is heavily based on the results of D2.1 and is an update to it. It is presented here as the culmination of the work done in all four of the WP2 tasks. After implementing the ToyLabs methodology from the previous iteration to WP3 and WP4 technical requirements and code, the experience gained, and the feedback obtained by the pilot partners with their hands-on experience helped form this new revised version of the methodology.

Specifically, the updates made to the Landscape Analysis are based on a combination of the updated methodology, as well as the needs for in-depth information stemming from T3.1 – Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis from WP3 – ToyLabs Added-Value Components design and development.

At the same time, the updates made to the ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-Creation Methodological Foundations, are based on the work done in T3.1 – Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis, T3.2-ToyLabs Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component, T3.3-ToyLabs Augmented Reality Component, T3.4-Partner Matching and Selection Component, T4.1-Collaboration Platform Design and Development, and T4.2-Added-Value Components Integration in their respective chapters. Additionally, feedback from T5.2-Mechanical Puzzle Toys Pilot and T5.3-Dolls & Accessories Pilot was used to update the methodological foundations.

WP	WP/Tasks	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
WP2	T2.1-ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-Creation Methodology																		
	T2.2-Toy Sector Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Approach																		
	T2.3-Augmented Reality for End User Feedback Collection																		
	T2.4-Partner Matching and Selection Methodology																		
ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development																			
WP3	T3.1-Technology Requirements and ToyLabs Components Analysis																		
	T3.2-ToyLabs Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component																		
	T3.3-ToyLabs Augmented Reality Component																		
	T3.4-Partner Matching and Selection Component																		
ToyLabs Integrated Platform Design and Development																			
WP4	T4.1-Collaboration Platform Design and Development																		
	T4.2-Added-Value Components Integration																		
	T4.3-ToyLabs Platform Verification and Validation																		
ToyLabs Piloting and Evaluation																			
WP5	T5.1-Pilot Preparation and Coordination Activities																		
	T5.2-Mechanical Puzzle Toys Pilot																		
	T5.3-Dolls & Accessories Pilot																		
	T5.4-Pilots Evaluation, Lessons Learnt and Impact Assessment																		

Figure 1-2 Relation with other Tasks & WPs

2 LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

2.1 SCOPE OF THE UPDATE IN LANDSCAPE ANALYSIS

For the update in the Landscape Analysis, a reverse approach was followed. In particular, firstly, an identification of the needs of the update in the methodology preceded, where feedback from interviews with the pilot partners and internal meetings (including the review meeting) was incorporated and translated into specific points that require deeper analysis and specification. Afterwards, these points that were later enriched and “assembled” into the new, integrated ToyLabs methodology, steered the update in the Landscape Analysis that can be found in the following sections.

In that view, the update in the Landscape Analysis focuses its efforts into:

- For Co-creation and Open Innovation: Feedback management in collaborative environments and specifically ways to ensure that previous, older feedback (e.g. rejected designs) is not being neglected and is efficiently analysed as well as that multi-stakeholder feedback is efficiently merged into one, representative, final solution. These approaches are also researched for the toy industry in particular.
- For Market Trend Analysis: Updates on the research for market trend analysis and social media analysis during the last months after the delivery of D2.1 with specific focus in the introduction of emotion instead of simple polarity detection as well as the differentiation of the analysis methods according to the social media source.
- For Augmented Reality: New technologies and tools introduced in 2017, which were not available at the time the first version of this document was produced, as well as a special focus on ARKit as the selected technological solution.
- For Partner Matching: Partner Matching as a driver of Business interoperability in Business-to-Business transaction systems as it targets among others to bring together and establish partnerships among companies that possess compatible structures, procedures and infrastructures.

In Figure 2-1, the figure that was first presented in D2.1 is made available in this deliverable too, in order to demonstrate the main terms of the landscape analysis in ToyLabs and their rationale. The joint domains of co-creation and open innovation operate as the foundation on which the methodology is based on, while the enabler is the Partner Matching domain, which supports and sets up Open Innovation and co-creation and finally Augmented Reality for feedback gathering and Market Trend Analysis are used to infuse Added Value into ToyLabs, and be used as tools to enhance extroversion and creativity towards the real market’s needs.

Figure 2-1 ToyLabs Methodology Landscape Analysis key terms

2.2 CO-CREATION AND OPEN INNOVATION

2.2.1 Feedback Management in Collaborative Environments

The ToyLabs project focuses its efforts into creating a collaborative environment, in which ToyLabs’ group of stakeholders can co-create products, exchange knowledge and give feedback (on designs, prototypes, final products etc.) with the aim of optimizing procedures, saving time and cutting costs.

Collaborative environments nowadays are manifested through multi-stakeholder platforms that are defined as “Decision-making bodies (voluntary or statutory) comprising different stakeholders who perceive the same resource management problem, realise their interdependence for solving it, and come together to agree on action strategies for solving the problem” (Steins, Edwards 1999)

The objective of an MSP is to enable the empowered and active participation of stakeholders in the search for solutions to a common problem (Faysse 2006). In order to effectively collaborate in multi-stakeholder platforms, (Lee, Lan Y. 2007) claimed that collaborative intelligence can be achieved by rallying knowledge from different domains and taking advantage of ICT technologies in order to achieve intellectual cooperation (Figure 1).

Figure 2-2 How to correctly collaborate in multi-stakeholder platforms (Lee, Lan Y. 2007)

The main scope of this chapter, concerning collaborative environments, is to uncover how feedback in these networks is generated, shared and stored, in other words the focus is on feedback management and how multi-stakeholder feedback is analysed in a way that multiple cross-sectorial feedback is merged into one final solution. Although literature has reported the significance of feedback in collaborative environments, research on feedback is quite fragmented and is full of anecdotal evidence and little inherent cohesion. However, an active effort was made to distil useful information about feedback from a variety of scientific publications.

Collaborative networks usually circulate ideas and feedback about past ideas/designs etc. with discussions and meetings in which stakeholders from every organisation participate actively and try to contribute to the final objective. Usually feedback from stakeholders who are relevant to the field being discussed will have greater weight to the conversation. However this presents the danger that feedback from stakeholders from a different sector may be ignored since these meetings tend to last for a long time and participants may not pay as much attention in some cases. That is why participants, depending on their sector, should pay very close attention to what is being said and distil any ideas/feedback relevant to their field and technical knowledge. This may also happen if stakeholders refuse to give feedback even though they have relevant ideas. This usually happens when there is a lack of trust and communication.

That is why, in order to create a better understanding of collaborative environments (Lee, Lan Y. 2007) described the following critical success factors for a high collaborative intelligence quotient:

- Establishing a group moderation, facilitation and satisfaction mechanism.
- Promoting of creative and unlimited thinking.
- Strong group membership consensus, interactions, and feedback.
- Providing quality assurance and peer review mechanisms for conflict resolution.
- Forming of a sufficient documented group memory or knowledge base.

When these conditions cannot be satisfied, it can lead to lack of communication and opinions/feedback that is neglected and stays unused. Given that these platforms are based on participation, ignoring feedback leads the person/entity that gave it to

have less incentive to do so again, which is very harmful in a collaborative environment.

Even though, the research literature is brimming with approaches of collaborative environments, the aforementioned problem of neglecting older feedback is not mentioned as often. It stands to reason then, that in such networks, the intent for old feedback is that it should be forgotten, especially when there is no system for documenting it. For example, (Josang, Ismail) introduced a forgetting factor and affirmed that the old feedback may be irrelevant and become obsolete with time; and they assigned a smaller weight to the old feedback. On the other hand, (Kan et al. 2001) developed a virtual reality collaborative environment (VRCE), that allowed participation by multiple collaborators in the design as well as archiving of discussions and feedback which allowed maturing of design ideas over time. The VRCE system records all users' conversation history by generating logs that contain valuable information of past designs which can be referenced by other users. In any case, whether old feedback is neglected or used for future reference depends on each specific case and on whether special care has been given to save feedback and knowledge exchange in a database in the platform (if one exists). Finally, (Ejarque et al. 2010) presented a framework which uses semantically enhanced historical data for predicting the behaviour of tasks and resources in the system, and allocating the resources according to these predictions.

The second area of interest of this chapter is how feedback and information from different domains is collected, analysed and merged into a final solution in the context of a collaborative environment. In general two main approaches were identified. Either feedback is saved in logs that require human effort to be analysed, or semantic technologies are used to organise feedback which is analysed by a decision support system to optimise procedures. Alternatively, Virtual Reality may be used to create a shared collaborative environment in which the above procedure is performed in real time. The main approaches that were identified from the bibliographic research are the following:

The VRCE platform by (Kan et al. 2001) that was already mentioned took advantage of virtual reality, by creating shared virtual environments in which multiple stakeholders can co-design in real time and give feedback by watching each other's viewpoint.

(Abramovici et al. 2016) describes an approach to a new generation of data management for an interdisciplinary, globally distributed development and continuous reconfiguration of smart products. The proposed solution is flexible, dynamic, has a high semantic content and considers both virtual product models as well as feedback data from the physical product along its whole lifecycle (digital product twin).

(Cheniti Belcadhi 2016) also proposed a feedback framework based on the Semantic Web for learning purposes.

(Xie et al. 2015) developed a model of collaborative healthcare system redesign by involving multiple healthcare stakeholders in the process. The required feedback was collected via interviews and analysed by having researchers read the transcripts, identify and group significant statements into themes while at the same time identifying links between them. In other words, in this case, multi-stakeholder feedback was analysed qualitatively by researchers and not by an automated system.

(Fazey et al. 2014) developed principles for evaluating knowledge exchange in interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder research by performing analyses of peer-reviewed evaluations of knowledge exchange from diverse disciplines and creating a typology of evaluations to guide discussions.

(Cvitanovic et al. 2015) identified barriers inhibiting knowledge exchange between scientists and decision makers and suggested options for overcoming these barriers such as knowledge co-production and knowledge brokers.

(Krusche et al.) Presented Rugby a software development methodology. Rugby presents a lightweight methodology to develop and release rapid prototypes and to learn from feedback comments in rapid parallel cycles. Specifically, user feedback is gathered by a feedback tracker and used as additional workflows in the software lifecycle model.

2.2.2 Feedback Management in the Toy Industry

Based on a qualitative research of toy manufacturers by personal interviews made by AIJU (2017), the analysis of the customer feedback is a very important aspect for their business.

Considering all the phases of creation of a new toy, toy manufacturers analyse the user feedback during the first stages (Immersion and concept design) and in the evaluation stage (That could affect during all the different stages). Some companies do not use feedback it in none of the phases (not shown in the chart).

Phases of new products creation in which user's feedback is used

Manufacturers in the toy industry collect feedback and analyse customer’s opinions by managing their own clients’ opinions, through their salespeople, analysing opinions on the web and based on sales of the products. In addition, they use their customer service channels and some visit their points of sale.

Ways of feedback collection

The most valued aspects for companies, when analysing user feedback are: knowing the positive and negative aspects of the products to use them as selling benefits, analysing preferences and needs to have a better knowledge of the target and knowing the information related to the attractiveness of the products.

Most important aspects related to customer's opinions

Regarding the information needs of companies in the toy industry, most of them prefer having trends' information for new products in March, after Nüremberg Fair and before starting designing the products. Some of the companies start the process in September/ October of the previous year, though, so this information will be applied (depending on the type of trend) for Christmas next year.

What concerns to stakeholders, the profiles which apply the information (or feedback) and knowledge of the trends are Management, Design, Marketing and Sales, in a joint work.

The management position mainly uses it to define and evaluate the product strategy and analyse costs and time.

In the design department, they use it mainly in the aesthetic part of the product development, adapting the product to the target.

Communication and marketing profiles are responsible for moving this information, also to focus on what is the best way to sell the product, determine the sector they should focus on, or define the style of the spots.

Finally, sales profiles use the information to evaluate the best way to present the product to the customer and prepare the sales brief.

Regarding to toy **retailers**, they are in direct contact with the families during the buying process (not when they are using it), and for this reason they have the opportunity to access to a huge amount of information.

The main problem of this huge amount of information, is the difficulty to analyse it and make conclusions, although “Big Data” techniques and tools are improving, is an aspect not being exploited 100% by the toy sector.

Retailers are aware of the importance of the revitalization of the point of sale and the number of activities (like speeches, exhibitions, new toys presentations, etc.) to increase the level of affluence to their shops is increasing in the most innovative part of the sector. Also, new buying styles in which the combination of the online and offline world and the second hand market are key aspects for them.

The toy sector is also aware of the importance of the product location and other marketing techniques in the moment of buying, and they invest an important amount of money for them in the creation of new stands, “try mes”, decorations, etc.

One of the most important aspects for the communication between manufacturers and retailers is the number of units sold. For this reason, a key aspect for both of them is the forecast of the number of units to produce, and this activity happens in most cases one year before the product is sold, especially for seasonal products.

Based on the level of success of the forecast activity, three different situations could be found:

- Underestimated number of units to produce: In this case scenario, a considerable number of unsatisfied consumers can be found, especially if it is an important toy for their children. This situation, is shown by the retailers as a problem with their customers and also as a lost business opportunity to them.
- Accurate forecast: If the last number of units that are in the stores have been sold during the last two or three days of the Christmas season, is a nearly perfect forecast for the toy manufacturer.
- Overestimated forecast: A lot of toys are and were occupying important place in the store that could be more profitable with new toys, these toys are perceived in a lot of cases as a problem and as non-successful toys. Their sustainability of these toys for the next season is put in doubt.

The huge importance of the historical data in this sector is an important barrier for the toy sector, because the main characteristic of an innovative product is the difficulty to compare it with other existent products, which difficult the forecast activity.

2.2.3 Key take-aways

This chapter performed a state-of-the-art research concerning feedback management in:

- collaborative environments in general by performing a bibliographic research and
- the toy industry by interviews performed with key stakeholders of the toy manufacturing sector.

Even though, stakeholders of the toy community consider feedback (from users, retailers etc.) to be very important for optimising procedures and making improvements on their products, there is a lack of academic papers that see feedback management as a real need in collaborative environments. That means that in most cases old and historical data/feedback are not taken into consideration and stay unused. In other words there is a growing need in the toy industry, but also in all collaborative environments in general, for solutions concerning the use of historic feedback as well as merging multi-stakeholder feedback in a single solution.

2.3 MARKET TREND ANALYSIS

2.3.1 Social Network Analysis for Trends Detection & Market Understanding

In deliverable D2.1 the field of social network analysis was described as well as its ties with the business and toy sectors in general. More specifically an exhaustive state of the art analysis of the sector was performed which was focused on trends identification through discovering patterns in order to predict the future.

In the previous deliverable two different flows were recognised concerning the Market Trend Analysis part of the ToyLabs holistic methodology:

- One flow for **feedback management and analysis** of a selected brand/product/competitor/etc.
- One flow for **trend detection and analysis** for a specific domain of interest (e.g. dolls, puzzles, etc.) which was sufficiently covered in D2.1.

In the current deliverable, the purpose of this chapter is to add to the previous analysis by identifying new approaches and research papers that were published between the two deliverables (D2.1 and D2.2). However, it should be mentioned that greater focus will be given on how social feedback is used to understand market trends as well as the role of emotion in understanding said social feedback.

According to (van Sophia Zyl 2009) an individuals' success in society depends on the shape and size of his social network and his ability to network and form connections with other social groups. Organisations who can harness this innate human ability to manage knowledge will be able to lower transactions costs and become more profitable. Nowadays, the abovementioned knowledge largely resides online in social networks (Facebook, twitter etc.) and other websites such as blogs where users voice their opinions (also known as social feedback). Social feedback is essential in the formation of a digital reputation and it allows users to rate the contributions of others (Boyd 2008; Brown, Duguid 2017).

By applying social network analysis, companies are able to gather the information that exists online and harness that knowledge in order to achieve an advantage against their competitors. Specifically, Social Networking can be used as a viral marketing tool, where people are encouraged to voluntarily pass marketing messages on through word-of-mouth (IBM 2007). Moreover, innovation can be encouraged by monitoring customer communications, feedback and opinions (Matuszak 2007; Tapscott, Williams 2006). However, in order for companies to take advantage of the capabilities that Social Networking offers, an online community needs to exist that generates content relevant to the company or its brands. A brand is defined as “the consumer perception and interpretation of a cluster of associated attributes, benefits and values” (Batey 2008) and these communities are better known as virtual brand communities which are defined as specialized, non-geographically

bound, online communities, based on social communications and relationships among a brand’s consumers (Valck et al. 2009).

Emotion plays a major role in understanding social feedback since every piece of text has a meaning which is usually conveyed through emotionally charged words. The analysis (manual or automatic) works by inspecting the polarity (positive or negative) of specific words in the text or the text in its entirety and shows what emotion the author is feeling towards a specific brand or a domain of interest. Manual analysis is performed by people (researchers, company employees etc.) that go through online texts and distil the meaning and emotions that it conveys according to their opinion. Automatic analysis is performed by applying specific algorithms and techniques (which were extensively covered in D2.1) and lexicons (that include a large number of words and the emotion they convey) on the text.

In the following part of this chapter, a number of approaches concerning Social Network Analysis, drawn from the bibliographic research, will be described. (Batey 2008) described how a consumer’s happiness can lead him to the loyalty loop of a brand in contrast to consumer discontent which has the opposite effect. As a result when a consumer wants to buy something he is mainly affected by other consumer’s feedback. In fact, (Cambria et al. 2017) claimed that in recommender systems, the products and services recommended to a person should be those that have been positively evaluated by other users with a similar personality type. Very often than not, consumer feedback is a mix of positive and negative consumer voices. A brand needs to focus on minimizing negative feedback and maximizing positive feedback to create a positive image in consumer’s mindscape. Consumer feedback can be manually analysed (although labour intensive) to find a brand’s health by analysing the meaning and emotion behind a text.

(Kumar et al. 2013) attempted to analyse health of brands by content analysis of the consumer feedback present on a brand’s Facebook page and categorisation of the feedback on the basis of benefits consumers derive. The authors suggested three categories of benefits; social (enjoyed by the society as a whole), physical (product benefits) and psychological (brand benefits). The findings for the sample used (three select brands) suggested that social benefits may play an important role in the growth of a brand in developed markets, whereas physical and psychological benefits dominate brand’s feedback in less developed markets.

(Hanusch, Tandoc 2017) explored the impact of user comments on journalism and described how feedback from users on social media can change not only the content of what is being presented (what the user wants to know instead of what the journalist wants to cover) but also the role of journalists. This proves that social feedback not only has an impact for specific products/people but also has the power to change the way an entire field operates.

(Xiang et al. 2017) used text analytics to comparatively examine three major online review platforms by analysing linguistic characteristics, semantic features, sentiments etc. of online reviews on these platforms. The purpose was to explore among others the data quality of the reviews in these platforms. Moreover, sentiment analysis was performed to the reviews to see the overall positivity/negativity in a site as well as the level of helpfulness of the reviews.

(Pathak, Pathak-Shelat 2017) performed sentiment analysis of netnographic (i.e. internet) data, aiming to explain the need to give special attention to negative sentiments expressed in virtual communities to aid brand managers in the process of brand co-creation by articulating brand communication targeted to specific audiences based on their shared passions and interests. Managing the negative interactions in the virtual communities and relationship development with members through non-commercial conversations should be the two main priorities for effective brand management. The authors claimed that sentiment analysis specifically helps to identify pain points and consumer sentiments at each stage of the shopper journey. The findings of the study endorsed the importance of offering and supporting communities as a valid marketing. The results of the analysis showed not only the polarity of sentiment (negative in this case) but also the points that led to the dissatisfaction of the customers proving that emotion is integral in understanding social feedback.

(Howells, Ertugan 2017) applied fuzzy logic to marketing in social media networks. While classical logic in Sentiment Analysis allows for only two values, positive or negative, 1 or 0, the Boolean values; fuzzy logic extends this to describe variables that are at best vague. In the case of sentiment analysis, this means that instead of positive and negative feelings. The objective of this study was to develop a model that can analyse the contents of a microblog (such as a tweet in Twitter) and be able to analyse customer feedback. The authors concluded that while using social media and online social networking to gather intelligence information for customer relationship management is fairly new, it is, however, a very serious development in the use of such data in monitoring social media comments for business intelligence.

(Giatsoglou et al. 2017) used sentiment analysis to extract opinions and sentiments about product reviews in Greek and in English recognizing the power of online reviews/feedback about a product for business and marketing professionals.

(Micu et al. 2017) examined restaurant customers' online activity following visits to said restaurants. Sentiment analysis was used to analyse customers' social media behaviour in terms of liking, rating, and reviewing restaurants, given that user-generated reviews and comments about experiences influence potential customers' decisions. The results of this study showed that gender and location of customers influence restaurant ratings. Furthermore, this article showed that sentiment analysis can help marketers by providing a useful tool for big data analysis. Specifically,

sentiment analysis can be used to interpret customer behaviour and highlight how presales, sales, and after-sales strategies can be improved.

(Crossley et al. 2017) introduced a new tool, SEANCE, which automatically analyses text features related to sentiment, cognition, and social order, among numerous other features. The tool is one of the first to be domain-general (usually domain specific terms play an integral role in the training of such tools), and the output allows users to develop theoretical inferences from their datasets.

(Tilara, Kumar 2017) focused on sentiment analysis of tweets on different issues collected from twitter. According to the authors, analysing reviews plays a crucial role in determining the growth of the product, since it deals with finding the opinions, identifying them and classifying the opinions and the sentiments behind them from text. These reviews play an important role in the marketing of a particular product and can change the market either in the favour of the product or downgrade the rating of that product. Reviews are the base of creating positive, negative or neutral waves in the market about any particular product, which in a way is making it easy for both consumers and sellers of the product to understand each other’s need.

2.3.2 Key take-aways

The present chapter aimed to perform an additional state-of-the-art research that will complement the one performed in the previous deliverable by finding more recent papers relevant to the field of Social Network Analysis. The bibliographic research showed that there are a variety of scientific papers that view social feedback analysis as an integral part in uncovering trends and public opinions in a variety of fields.

However, even though, Social Network Analysis can be seen as a very useful tool in a variety of domains two barriers still stand out:

1. Up to this point, not many papers exist that try to study Social Network Analysis in regards to the manufacturing sector (i.e. co-production), since most papers view it as a powerful tool for marketing purposes and thus study it exclusively under this premise.
2. There are even fewer attempts in trying to develop a unified methodology/ approach/platform that effectively performs Social Network Analysis in multiple domains, the reason being that in order to train a system to perform such a job an incredible amount of cross-domain data need to be gathered and used to train the tool.

In summary, even though the usefulness of Social Network Analysis for trends detection has been widely recognized, the field is still underutilized in many domains.

2.4 AUGMENTED REALITY FOR FEEDBACK GATHERING

2.4.1 Landscape Review Update

In Deliverable D2.1, an overview of the status, research results and applications of Augmented Reality technologies for gathering feedback from end-users has been provided. However, thanks to the breakthroughs in AR algorithms and tools introduced almost every day, AR on smartphones has been soaring to new heights. Under those terms, the present section presents the most recent developments forming the landscape in the AR applications field.

- According to Haibin Ling (Ling 2017), the rapid rise in AR use stems from four main developments:
- the pervasiveness of low-cost visual sensors, such as phone cameras, which created the foundation for AR consumerism;
- progress in environmental perception algorithms, such as visual simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM), which has provided key guidance for fusing virtual information and reality;
- advances in optics, which largely pushed the development of consumer-level AR displays; and
- the maturity of multimedia techniques, which enriched the content and styles of AR applications.

On the basis of those developments 2017 has been “the year of augmented reality” for some of the top tech companies. Facebook presented its AR Camera platform, while Google continued to show additions to Tango as well as its new AR app Google Lens and has announced AR Core, a platform for building augmented reality apps on Android which is in Developer Preview stage at the time this deliverable is being compiled. In parallel, Apple has just released ARKit, a platform which the company describes as the largest AR platform in the world. The ARKit is a core technology, described by Apple as “a new framework that brings augmented reality to hundreds of millions of mobile devices by allowing developers to easily build unparalleled AR experiences”¹.

Product design and early feedback collection are activities that can be severely affected by the new AR capabilities offered. Development teams become more globally distributed, making difficult to get everyone involved to review a product design in a timely manner, collect all the information needed for the review, and capture feedback for future action. According to Deloitte Insights², augmented reality is a key for enabling companies to digitize the product-design process and there are

¹ <https://www.abc.org/tech-advances/apple-unveils-largest-ar-platform-in-the-world/1988.article>

² <https://www2.deloitte.com/insights/us/en/focus/signals-for-strategists/augmented-and-virtual-reality-enterprise-applications.html>

already a few demonstrations of applying AR technologies for design in several high-tech domains like aerospace, automotive and several industrial products. Because AR enables designers to model and test detailed virtual prototypes without physical construction, it can cut development time, reduce production costs, and yield better products by increasing understanding earlier in the process. An interesting example, and good practice at the same time, could be considered BMW; the company has deployed AR to design and prototype virtual automobiles, making the design process faster and cheaper³.

2.4.2 Key take-aways

Apparently Augmented Reality technologies are being evolved day by day and new technological advances are being announced from teams of researchers of both the academic and the commercial sector.

By combining the landscape analysis performed and presented in Deliverable D2.1 with the recent advances described above, taking advantage of Augmented Reality technologies in order to support manufacturers reduce product development lifecycle, as proposed and implemented in ToyLabs project, can serve as a good practice for the future of the AR manufacturing applications.

Major software and service providers have started offering solutions for building AR-based applications. For the terms of ToyLabs, in order to engage as many end-users as possible, it's important to keep the whole offering user friendly and make it work with existing hardware. Given that Apple has already released the AR Kit for iOS devices (iPhones, iPads etc.) and on the other hand Google's AR Core is still in developer preview stage (so cannot be actually incorporated and tested), it has been decided during the ToyLabs interim review meeting that the project will develop an Augmented Reality solution for iOS devices which is acceptable in terms of the huge number of Apple mobile devices worldwide. The development of a similar approach based on AR Core in order to support Android devices is considered as a future step during the exploitation/ commercialization phase of the ToyLabs platform after the end of the project, when the Google Platform is expected to be officially released.

³<https://www.accenture.com/gr-en/success-bmw-digital-transformation-augmented-reality>

2.5 PARTNER MATCHING

2.5.1 Partner Matching as a driver for Business Interoperability

Partner matching is among the core elements that drive business interoperability in Business-to-Business transaction systems as it targets among others to bring together and establish partnerships among companies that possess compatible structures, procedures and infrastructures. The latter are though in most cases of heterogeneous nature and constitute a bottleneck for rapid production execution. This fact is particularly evident in the case of collaborative and open innovation-based manufacturing, where the ostensibly ensured advantage of having large pools of collaborators that guarantee the infusion of innovation in production and employing flexible production schedules suffers greatly from the existence of incompatibilities between the working characteristics of different potential partners, incompatible information flows and different processing techniques.

Research showcases in fact that the absence of well-defined, interoperable components in the different business transaction system layers results undoubtedly in situations where the larger a pool of collaborators is, the more difficult coordination and proper execution of orders becomes (European Commission). The availability of such components is considered more specifically crucial at:

- the level of semantics, where of interest are a set of items ranging from partner organisation and product descriptions, to common vocabularies for automated process execution;
- the technological level, that is the level that concerns IT system interconnection, but also
- the strategic level where the purpose is that of governing manufacturing networks.

The absence of such components is therefore severely thinning any advantage that a collaborative and open-innovation driven approach can deliver (Markaki et al. 2012).

In recent years, several approaches have been formulated (Zacharewicz et al. 2017), offering solutions to interoperability problems, the latter ranging from simple business interoperability solutions on the basis of common business models and core components technical specifications for information sharing, which address mostly peer-to-peer collaboration in business alliances and cover generally the lower interoperability layers, to Dynamic Manufacturing Networks management methodologies that pursue to orchestrate manufacturing networks in an end-to-end

fashion at the semantics and technical levels (Papazoglou et al. 2015; Carlos Agostinho et al. 2016).

In fact, it is the concept of Dynamic Manufacturing Networks or DMNs, where extensive emphasis has been given to partner matching and selection (Viswanadham, Gaonkar 2003), as the former describes large pools of prospective collaborators, where the sharing of information about issues, such as their capacities, schedules, and cost structures, allows them to spontaneously engage into collaborations. This gives a significant advantage over traditional collaboration networks and allows novel supply chain methods to be deployed. Such an advantage relies heavily on enhanced business interoperability, calling for solutions that embrace entities of different nature, size and technological infrastructure. This further promotes interoperability, making no discrimination between IT-rich and IT-poor organisations, suggesting in most of the cases low cost, reusable components, and providing solutions that are sector and operation-agnostic.

2.5.2 Key take-aways

Of interest to the Partner Matching and Selection component of the ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-creation Methodology are the following observations:

- Business interoperability is highly relevant when it comes to initiating collaborative processes, such as the ones foreseen by the ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-creation Methodology.
- The ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-creation Methodology may benefit from advanced DMN management methodologies, as it involves multiple and diverse stakeholders with multiple roles along the toy manufacturing process.

3 TOYLABS OPEN INNOVATION AND CO-CREATION METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS

3.1 UPDATE ON STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFICATION

In D2.1 “ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation Integrated Methodology – v1”, the main ToyLabs stakeholders, were identified, along with a description for them and their value proposition in the toy design cycle.

Although, all these stakeholders can be considered as potential ToyLabs solution users, the importance of their role in the platform is not equal for all of them. The role of certain identified stakeholder types is central according to the ToyLabs vision and respective platform, whereas the role of others is supportive.

The following table demonstrates the intensity of the expected platform’s use for each identified stakeholder type (in Low-Medium-High values) along with a brief description for them. For more information on the description of the stakeholders and their value proposition, one may refer on Table 3-1 of the previous deliverable, D2.1.

Table 3-1 Identified ToyLabs Stakeholders and Expected Role in the Platform

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	ROLE IN THE PLATFORM (Low, Medium, High)
Manufacturers	A person/ group/ company owning or running a manufacturing plant. Responsible of the whole toy creation process.	High
Inventors	People/ companies that offer new toy ideas/ concepts/ designs usually to manufacturers or distributors	High
Designers	People/ companies that offer new toy ideas/ concepts/ designs usually to manufacturers or distributors + help the evolution of other people’s concepts or ideas to designs	High
Engineers	People/ companies that offer to help with the evolution of conceptual designs into more detailed states for their mass production	Medium
User experts	Companies/ persons that are experts and have the necessary infrastructure to test concepts,	High

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION	ROLE IN THE PLATFORM (Low, Medium, High)
	designs, prototypes and final products with final users (parents and children usually).	
Marketers	People/ companies who are experts in the promotion of toys. Main activities: advertising, social media management, product placement, sales and contact with distributors	Medium
Market and design researchers	People/ companies who are experts in the detection of market and user needs.	Medium
Safety experts	People/ companies who are experts in analysing and applying all toy safety standards	High
Suppliers	Companies that provide the necessary material, components and/ or machinery required by the manufacturers	Low
Distributors	Companies that own toy stores or specific spaces for selling toys	Low
Lawyers	Representatives of clients in a court of law or advisors in other legal matters.	Low
FabLabs	A small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication. (Fabrication Laboratories)	High

3.2 METHODOLOGY DEFINITION

3.2.1 Introduction

The purpose of this section is to provide an update on the methodology presented in the respective section (section 3.2) of the previous deliverable, D2.1 “ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation Integrated Methodology – v1”.

The months that followed the submission of D2.1, the first two releases of the ToyLabs Added-Value Components and the Integrated Collaboration Platform were delivered. The progress in the platform’s development as well as the fruitful discussions among the consortium’s partners during this period imposed the need for certain updates in the presented ToyLabs methodology, both on what concerns the ToyLabs methodology for Open Innovation and Co-creation, as well as the methodological foundations under the notions of “Market Trends and Social Feedback

Analysis”, “End-user Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality” and “Partner Matching and Selection”. Furthermore, the interim review meeting that took place on November 2017 provided guidelines and directions for the following months of the ToyLabs project duration that were effectively analysed and capitalised on the updated methodology.

In the context of the following sections, the updated methodologies for the four identified ToyLabs domains are presented, driven by the aforementioned feedback. However, since this is the final methodological deliverable for the ToyLabs project, emphasis is not only stressed in the differentiations from the first version of the ToyLabs methodology (as this was presented in D2.1), but instead the whole approach, in the form of steps, is described, in order to provide to the reader a comprehensive, integrated view of the proposed ToyLabs concept and respective methodology.

The ultimate goal is to deliver a methodological framework that can be used in the hands of any toy manufacturing company and specifically SMEs for attaching more value to their design processes and new product development activities. The three methodologies for “Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis”, “End-user Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality” and “Partner Matching and Selection” can be considered both as standalone methodologies, leveraged by any toy manufacturer that wants to achieve a very specific goal, but also combined, under the Open Innovation and Co-creation Holistic methodology, to provide as modules of a larger methodology that aspires to completely change toy design process, reducing time to market and costs and increasing market success rates, especially for SMEs.

3.2.2 Open Innovation and Co-creation Holistic Methodology

The ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation Methodology refers to a complete methodological approach developed under the scope of the project’s concept and objectives. The methodology describes all the steps, the interconnections and the flow of information and actions for adopting in practice an open innovation model in the toys’ creation process with the active involvement of multiple stakeholders. Without eliminating other roles, the main stakeholders to which ToyLabs - as a project - and the Open Innovation and Co-creation methodology - as an approach – focuses are:

- Toy Manufacturers
- Fabrication Laboratories (FabLabs)
- Safety Experts/ Environmental Experts
- Childhood Experts
- Market Experts & Representatives
- Distributors and Retailers

Stemming from the research performed since the publication of the previous version of the ToyLabs methodology, it was decided that Distributors and Retailers should be directly added as platform users. Although ToyLabs focuses on the innovation and co-creation side of the market-aware design and certification of new or improved toys, the significance of the ability of the platform to act as a marketplace of competences in the search of collaborators in the creation of new products, led to the conclusion that this force can also be used to further explore the openness of the methodology and the platform itself, towards a direct relation to the actual market. In other words, the toy design hub described in ToyLabs can act as a hub for ideas and products aimed more towards the end market.

Market experts and representatives have a clear understanding of the needs and trends for the marketability of a new product, but they will not themselves place the orders. Although their feedback is valuable, they are not expected to be personally invested in the success and the sales of the new products. On the other hand, distributors and retailers are always on the hunt for products that are new, innovative and, in the end, attractive enough to generate revenue. Their direct inclusion in the platform has a twofold effect. First, they can provide feedback on the design of new toys and second, when involved in the design process, they can become invested on innovative design ideas that they have contributed on, and, as a result, also invest in acquiring the end products for their distribution networks or stores. In this sense, ToyLabs can become an end-to-end business solution for the SME toy industry.

In addition to those stakeholders, the methodology also refers to the role of “Product Owner”, which can be any member of the ToyLabs network who has an idea for a new toy and wishes to invest on it. Usually the role of the product owner belongs to a toy manufacturing organisation, however there are cases that, for example, a retailer, a FabLab, a Safety Expert or even a childhood expert may have an idea for a new toy and through ToyLabs may try to collaborate with a manufacturer in order to bring this idea to life and to the market. In this case the Product Owner role is being assigned to the originator of the idea, while the manufacturer supports the implementation of the product on the basis of specific contractual agreement made between the product owner and the manufacturer, clarifying the roles and the rights of each party. In this sense, a product owner can be any user of the platform.

The phases of the ToyLabs Open Innovation and Co-creation methodology, the flow and the interconnections among the phases are presented in the following figure. The whole approach has been based on:

- The industry survey performed and described in D1.1 (WP1)
- The high-level user requirements presented in D1.2 (WP1)
- An extensive literature review work and development of an integrated methodology performed under WP2.

- The feedback generated from WP5 “ToyLabs Piloting and Evaluation” and specifically the work done for D5.1 and D5.2

Figure 3-1 ToyLabs Methodology Diagram

The methodology, as presented in the previous diagram and analysed per phase in the current section, has been inspired by the FITMAN⁴ Verification & Validation Methodology for the development of software for manufacturing enterprises. In practice, while building on the idea of an enhanced V-Model (ISTQB 2015), the ToyLabs approach introduces a totally new view as far as it concerns product development in the toy industry. It has to be mentioned, additionally, that with a few modifications the approach could be probably applied in other Creative Industries as well.

In principle, the ToyLabs Open Innovation & Co-creation methodology is based on the fact – which has been also pointed out in WP1 deliverables – that in order to improve the whole product development process it is important to include multiple

⁴ <http://www.fitman-fi.eu>

stakeholders in the process, even from the early stages of the development of a new product. On the other hand, since for a sector like the toys, which is addressed to children and teenagers, having a well-defined approach for validating the end-products is a very crucial and sensitive issue. Specific emphasis has been given in utilising different types of product assessment and validation activities, in a way that fits the industry standards and the toy safety issues, which are of highest importance.

3.2.2.1 *Immersion*

The immersion phase stands at the beginning of the creation of any new product, especially of those belonging in the creative industries domains. As thoroughly described in D1.1 and D1.2, immersion refers to understanding potential market needs and getting inspired, in order to create a new product or an improved version of an existing one. In the toy industry, this phase does not include designing a new toy – sometimes not even drafting it – but getting inspired about the main characteristics, appearance and features that could lead to a new toy (or to a new/ improved version of a toy).

The most important part of the immersion phase is to understand the actual market needs. This can be done by getting the complete picture of the toy’s category market under consideration, through listening to potential customers, either they will be the end users of the products or the retailers and understanding what the characteristics are to be included in a new product, in order to increase the probability that they become commercially successful. Large companies in the toy industry do support this phase by spending significant amounts of money in several types of market research activities, while sometimes they rely on hiring inventors who have previously proven that they have deep knowledge of the market’s needs. However, for SMEs things are not so easy. Hiring successful toy inventors or designers is not actually an option due to budget issues, while the same stands for buying expensive market research studies. Now, SMEs mostly rely on the inputs that their marketing departments may have directly from existing B2B or B2C customers, which only a few times do have specific proposals that could become the basis for a new product, although they can consult on the marketability of a product, once they are exposed to it.

On the other hand, specifically B2C customers, owning toy retail stores, are closest to the daily massive product testing that happens on their premises than any other stakeholder. Their customers, may they be parents or their children, provide feedback about their hands-on experience with the toys all the time. Even though they wouldn’t be able to contribute heavily on the design aspect of creating new toys, retailers can be very effective in pinpointing errors or potential improvements to existing ones. As the design of new products rarely involves reinventing the wheel, opinions on apparent shortcomings of designs of products that are already circulated

in the market can be the driving force to create new ones, that either are alterations of existing ones, or that are incorporating these improvements in new ones.

The ToyLabs approach considers that, nowadays, social media and in general Web 2.0 channels are valuable sources of data, which when analysed and processed accordingly, may offer insights (to be used in immersion phase of a new product) which sometimes cannot be acquired even through professional market research studies. Based on this fact, the ToyLabs open innovation and co-creation holistic methodology incorporates a market trends and social feedback analysis approach about how valuable information and insights that could significantly support the immersion phase for a new or enhanced toy can be extracted or produced.

From the stakeholders' point of view, the ToyLabs approach, apart from supporting Toy Manufacturers during the immersion phase, has a wider scope: to pave the way for anyone who has an initial idea for a new toy, to explore whether the idea is innovative and if it follows current market trends. For ToyLabs, anyone can become the initiator of a new toy product – so the approach described here doesn't only refer to toy manufacturers but to anyone who has an idea and wishes to identify market trends and needs, in order to validate and further improve it.

3.2.2.2 *Concept Definition*

The concept definition phase of the ToyLabs methodology consists of the required actions for setting up the development of a new toy. Specifically, concept definition begins from deciding and writing down the main characteristics of the product under consideration and finishes with the conceptual design of the toy. The main scope of the ToyLabs approach regarding this phase is to find partners for supporting the realisation of the idea leading not only to the conceptual design of the new product but also to an initial feasibility assessment. In case the owner of the idea (and of the product to be developed) is a toy manufacturer, the concept definition and the immersion phases could be considered as one phase consisting of two activities. On the other hand, for the case that the idea owner doesn't have resources of a toy manufacturer, (e.g. product design skills, feasibility assessment skills, engineering skills etc), the concept definition phase includes the process of finding the most appropriate manufacturer and creating a partnership between the idea (product) owner and the manufacturer. At this stage, it is also agreed between them how the ownership/property rights of the product to be developed will be shared among the involved parties (usually a toy manufacturer and the owner of the idea for a new toy). This can be any type of agreement: the product owner may keep 100% of the product IPRs or may share them with the manufacturer. If the product owner is a retailer or distributor, that agreement can act directly as a commission. At the same time, it is being agreed who is the one who shall manage the next steps of the product development process: it can be the idea/product owner in case he/she has the technical skills to do so, or the manufacturer acting for the product owner.

From a methodological point of view, a product owner can at this phase find and select the most appropriate manufacturer to collaborate with, by following the methodological steps defined in the ToyLabs Partner Matching and Selection Methodology.

Regarding feasibility assessment, ToyLabs considers that depending on the exact toy sector, the country and the available information, the feasibility check for a new product at the conceptualisation phase is case-specific. The same stands for IPR checks to verify that there are no conflicts regarding intellectual property issues.

3.2.2.3 *Design*

The design phase includes the development of the detailed design of the new product, including details about materials, engineering and required processing. ToyLabs proposes an enhanced iterative design approach based on collaboration with external parties who belong in the ToyLabs network. Specifically, ToyLabs considers that the initial product design is shared with one or more FabLabs as well as with safety experts in order to provide feedback and recommendations on the design.

The collaborative design approach of ToyLabs considers that for each new product a number of collaborators (normally one or more FabLab(s) and a safety expert) have to be selected at this stage by the product owner.

The contribution of the FabLabs mostly refers to technical insights regarding the materials, the processing and the technical feasibility of the design, however is not limited to that. Depending on the case and the experience of the design team of the product owner/ manufacturer, the FabLabs may also proceed directly to proposed changes on the design (to be approved by the product owner), or they may transform the 2D designs into 3D. Creating detailed 3D designs is required in order to proceed to the prototyping phase which follows, so at this stage the contribution of the FabLabs can be crucial.

Regarding the workflow of the process, an iterative approach is being adopted. The lead designer of the product owner shares the initial designs of the new toy, regardless of the level of detail they have, and asks from the FabLabs that have been included in the project to provide their feedback, either in general or on specific details of the design. The FabLab(s) may either provide comments or create enhanced, or CAD versions of the designs and share them back. Afterwards the designer may create a new design, incorporating, either all, or some of the recommended changes, and share it again with the involved stakeholders. The process continues in an iterative way until the designer or the product owner the design final, at least for this stage.

At any time during the above process, as well as after finalising the design, the product owner may also include safety experts, asking them to provide recommendations regarding the compliance of the design to the safety standards that

apply for the specific toy category. Although compliance check is something that can be done only after finalising the product, the provision of recommendations/ feedback by safety experts at this early stage is considered crucial in the ToyLabs approach in order to reduce costs incurred if any toy-safety related issue is identified at a later stage.

3.2.2.4 *Prototyping*

The scope of prototyping is to create tangible prototypes of the product being designed, in order for it to be assessed by pilot end-users and to get the initial feeling of how the final product will look like and operate. In other words, prototypes are created to simulate the final solution in a way that an end-user can interact with them, and evaluate them, which can be considered as early testing of the actual final product. Prototyping is not, of course a one-off process, but an iterative one: the first prototypes are usually cheap and simple and tend to evolve into more complex and detailed ones.

The main characteristics that ToyLabs adds to the (typical) process from a methodological point of view are the following:

- Finding the most appropriate FabLabs in terms of experience and equipment for building the prototypes, through the partner matching methodology.
- Taking advantage of the different locations of the FabLabs to build different versions of the prototype in each case, adapted respectively to the local environment, culture or needs – this may be limited to translating any written text to the local language – or to more important radical changes e.g. dolls having different hair or skin colour.
- Using an Augmented Reality approach, for acquiring feedback from groups of experts and end-user, when the tangible prototypes aren't available for any number of reasons, like cost, the unavailability of a sufficient number of prototypes for all testers or on different locations, and the need to obtain preliminary feedback before proceeding with the construction of the prototypes, if these are too expensive or difficult to make. Taking advantage of Augmented Reality technologies can amount to an experience closer to the one from a tangible object, than designs or 3D renders on paper and computer screens.

Prototyping is the most important phase of the methodology, regarding the collaboration between Product Owners, Manufacturers, FabLabs, and Safety Experts, which acted as the basis for the whole open innovation and co-creation concept of ToyLabs. Especially as far as FabLabs are concerned, while in the previous phases their role was limited to supporting the design process and giving feedback to the product owners, in the prototyping phase they are the focus. After the design of the new toy has been finalised, the product owner uses the partner matching and selection approach to identify which FabLabs – members of the ToyLabs network – have the

competencies to create prototypes of the specific toy. After selecting one or more of them, depending on one hand on the financial offer made and on the other hand on whether the product owner is interested in the location of the company, and proceeding to contractual agreements regarding the services to be offered, the manufacturer sends the designs and the requirements for the prototypes to be produced. The prototypes may be the same for all the FabLabs that have been selected for the specific product, or they may be different, to create ‘localised’ versions of the toys in each market.

The next step is the development of the 3D model which is required for producing the prototypes. This is something that both the designers of the manufacturer, if there is one, and the designers of the FabLabs may be able to do, so it’s up to the agreement between the parties whether the FabLabs shall provide such a service or not. Nevertheless, after agreeing on the 3D designs, one or more prototypes of the toy are produced by the FabLabs. Depending on the category of the toy product and whether it’s one of the first iterations of prototyping, the produced item may have significant simplifications compared to the end-product. These simplifications may refer to appearance (e.g. colouring) or to functional/ operational aspects of the design (e.g. with less degrees of freedom of the moving parts). This may need to be the case for complex designs, or to reduce cost, especially if prototyping is scheduled to be performed in many iterations, or when prototyping is very difficult to be done in FabLabs, due to the constraints of their equipment and manufacturing methods. The Augmented Reality solution in this case can fill the gap in between tangibility and functionality, by allowing the testers to both have access to a physical object, as well as being able to experience its use in a close to reality environment.

By producing an AR 3D object at the same time as creating the tangible prototype, the FabLab or the Product Owner can directly assemble expert and focus groups, consisting of childhood experts, market experts, end customers (including end users/children if no safety hazards are identified), and safety experts. This feedback is then sent back to the product owner to improve the designs, or solve safety issues, and then proceed to the next iteration of the process, by creating the next batch of prototypes, until it is decided that no more modifications need to be made, and the design can move to pre-production.

3.2.2.5 *Pre-production / Pre-series manufacturing*

The scope of the phase is to set the manufacturing process up and to produce the first series of the product to be used both for functional, operational and safety assessment purposes, as well as for getting feedback from market experts to build the product’s marketing strategy. The following steps of the ToyLabs methodology refer to the distinct types of testing and assessment of the final product, based on the pre-series manufacturing performed.

In this phase, ToyLabs’ tools are used to enhance parts of the regular process followed by most companies. From the development and assessment of the different prototypes, performed in the previous phase, alternative customised/ localised versions of the same product may have been decided, so the pre-production and pre-series manufacturing of each alternative version of the final product needs to be planned separately.

Furthermore, the experience acquired by the FabLabs and the feedback and technical consultation they may provide, based on the prototyping process (e.g. regarding specific attention that needs to be shown for sensitive toy parts), can be considered for optimally setting up the pre-production of the product. Similar to the prototyping phase, the feedback mechanism remains a tool that can be used here.

3.2.2.6 *Operational Assessment*

The operational assessment is the first step of the ToyLabs product verification and validation process which refers to the actual final product before it gets distributed to the market. The scope is to verify that the end product has been built according to the specifications, as described during its detailed design, functionally, aesthetically and according to the quality and safety standards set.

In case an inconsistency has been identified during this phase (e.g. on quality, functionality, durability etc.), it has to be examined whether the prototype on which the final item has been based on also had the same issue. If this is the case, then the process goes back to the Prototyping phase for refinement and, while a new pre-series manufacturing based on the amended model is implemented.

On the other hand, if the issue does not appear on the developed prototype, then the setup of the production is re-examined (from material selection and mould development up to parts assembly), to identify and fix the issue before proceeding to the next phases.

The operational assessment itself does not involve external parties to the manufacturer, as the product must be checked versus its own requirements and detailed design. When further feedback is required, such as the need for a redesign and the production of more prototypes, the stakeholders involved are the product owner, the manufacturer and the FabLabs for providing production insights based on the developed prototypes.

3.2.2.7 *Safety & Environmental Impact Assessment*

The safety and environmental impact assessment refers to the actual validation of the final toy based on International and EU safety and environmental standards. While, during the ToyLabs process, consultation and feedback is being provided by safety and environmental experts in several phases of the process, here all the tests

required take place to confirm that the product has all the safety characteristics to get certified based on existing safety standards. As far as environmental impact assessment is concerned, this includes validating that the product itself, including the materials used and the production method applied, comply to environmental standards and rules and on the other hand the estimation of the environmental impact of the production process and of the product itself, which is of high value for toy-companies which rely on green strategies and environmentally friendly approaches.

In case any issue is identified during this phase, especially if it concerns a hazard and as the toy sector is very sensitive in safety issues, then it is examined whether there has been a design flaw as the main reason for the product not passing safety tests or if it's an issue of the production. This is done as a collaboration between the manufacturer and the the toy safety expert with the support of the involved FabLabs if required. In any case finding and verifying the root of the problem is crucial as the process needs to return to either to the design phase, if the design itself had issues not earlier identified, or to the phases to follow it.

3.2.2.8 *Experts/ End Users Assessment*

The ToyLabs open innovation and co-creation methodology involves experts of the childhood domain early in the process, to assist with the conceptualisation, the design, and the testing of the products, according to the requirements, the market's needs, and the insights provided by a wide spectrum of childhood professionals. The assessment performed at this stage aims to collect feedback on the actual final product by:

- Childhood experts, examining the toy from an educational and/or psychological impact view
- End users, testing the toy and providing feedback about its main advantages and disadvantages
- Toy market experts, providing feedback regarding marketing issues like packaging, product appearance and promotion
- Retailers, assessing and suggesting the product's in-store placement, possible retail performance, pricing, demographics, expected customer conversion ratio etc.

At this stage, the feedback received only in very few cases may lead back to previous steps of the process. If the assessment performed has a totally negative outcome, then the product owner has to identify whether the initial concept was out of market or if the way that is has been implemented failed. However, given the fact that the entire process is based on getting feedback during the early phases of product development, this is not considered a possible case. The results of the assessment performed at this phase are expected to mainly act as input to the next phase referring

to the commercialisation of the product. In other terms, to identify and provide tips to be taken into account by the marketing department of the product owner, so that the way that the toy will be promoted to the market to fits its characteristics and to emphasise on its main advantages considered as important for the selection of the toy by the end customer.

3.2.2.9 Commercialisation

The ToyLabs methodological approach refers to the development of a toy from its inception to its creation and the setup of its production. The commercialisation process mostly refers to the marketing and sales operations which are not covered by the core ToyLabs lifecycle. The scope of the ToyLabs process however is to provide to the marketing experts the results of multiple types of evaluation of the product, regarding safety, environmental impact, educational value, main advantages etc., in order this information to be combined and taken into account for building the product’s marketing strategy. Additionally, as retailers can provide feedback on the actual measurable impact of a new product on the market, as well as in-store marketing tips and experiences, based on observational data, sales data, including information on placement, pricing, packaging, and promotion as observed in the stores themselves.

Furthermore, for ToyLabs what is crucial at this phase is to setup a mechanism for collecting feedback to be taken into account not for the product itself (as it’s already in the market), but during the immersion and conceptualisation phases either for any toy belonging in the same category or for developing an updated/ enhanced version of an existing toy, taking into account the good and the bad feedback reports of the version already in the market.

3.2.3 Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Methodology

The ToyLabs methodology “Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis” is decomposed in two separated, but with many common “technical” parts, flows, as follows:

- 1) One flow for **social feedback management and analysis** of a selected brand/product/competitor/etc. The objective of this workflow is to give to the manufacturer (or any other interested user of the methodology) insights on his brand image and the crowd perception about his products, as this is reflected in social media, as well as the opportunity to make comparisons among the appeal of his brand/products and his competitors ones. In this context, both the frequency of social mentions about specified brands/products and the sentiment implied in them are being monitored and compared.
- 2) One flow for **market trend detection and analysis** for a specific domain of interest (e.g. dolls, puzzles, etc.). According to this flow, a relevant toy domain is specified and analysed exploiting the vivid discussions in social media and web sources in order to detect relevant concepts and the sentiment encrypted in their social mentions, unveil hidden dependencies and come up with potentially unknown future trends for the specified domain of interest.

Furthermore, insights can also be gained into the expected adoption of a new toy design by a somewhat uninvolved crowd, i.e. a diverse crowd that was not specifically questioned to provide opinions on specific ideas.

In the previous deliverable, D2.1, focus was given mainly on the description of the methodological steps, in a high level, without making explicit the differences in their application among the two different workflows. In the present deliverable, the feedback gained from the progress that emerged, after the delivery of D2.1, for the Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis component, in the context of WP3, is being incorporated here and decomposed to fit the respective methodology.

Along the following lines, the updated Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis methodology is described in the form of discrete steps, pointing out the updates from the work that has been already documented in D2.1, providing though an integrated, standalone representation of the final methodology.

The goal of the presented methodology is to come up with a common framework to guide toy manufacturers and designers through acquiring competitive intelligence from social media.

In that view, six core steps are being identified, in direct correlation with the steps and processes identified from the landscape analysis, as well as one preparatory step, step 0, that is a step performed outside the platform among the involved stakeholders in order to configure the analysis to follow to their specific needs and their industry’s specific characteristics.

The following figure presents a high-level view of the steps of the methodology, as well as a brief, bulleted description of the processes considered for each of them. Each of these steps will be thoroughly described along the following lines.

Figure 3-2 Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Final Methodology for both flows

The main updates with respect to the previous deliverable, as these are revealed in the figure above, have to do firstly with the clarification of the steps each defined flow encompasses, but also the provision of one additional step/level, after the data collection and before preprocessing. This additional step emerged as essential from the work implemented in WP3 and documented in D3.2 & D3.3. More updates have been also considered, either in the form of changes or deepening of the analysis, with respect to each step and can be found in the description of each step along the following lines.

3.2.3.1 Preparatory step – Step 0

This step is responsible for preparing the ground appropriately for the analysis that follows, taking into consideration the needs and approach of the toy manufacturer in question and the industry/product type he represents.

As seen also in Figure 3-2, it is decomposed in two sequential steps; the preparation of the Master Harvester and the preparation of the Organisation's Harvester, with the first being mandatory and the second one an optional step.

According to this approach, the Preparation for the Master Harvester has to do with all preparatory steps (as these are described below) to prepare social media analysis for the toy industry in general. Specifically, a first, “default”, preparation is being implemented that is general enough in order to apply effectively to the interests

of any toy manufacturer. That means that the sources and key-phrases defined, as will be described below, are generic, defining and characterizing the toy industry.

On the other hand, the preparation for the per organization harvesting, is optional, giving the manufacturer the opportunity to further expand and better represent his domains of interest for the analysis that will follow.

The reason for this change, is that both preparation and – even more - harvesting (i.e. the step 1: Data Collection) are time consuming tasks that also require understanding of the way harvesting and analysis operates. In particular, although this methodology is addressed to a general user with no specific expertise in data and social media analysis, manufacturers and toy designers, due to a different orientation, frequently find it difficult to understand how to configure Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis process appropriately. Furthermore, there are times that the analysis needs to run quickly, e.g. when a new product needs to enter the market in a short time period. Therefore, since one of the ToyLabs methodology main value propositions is the reduction of the time to market for a new toy and since the methodology aspires to offer to any SME toy manufacturer the opportunity to initiate an alternative process for the creation of new, innovative products, the existence of a Master Harvester configured by the ToyLabs consortium’s experts has been considered necessary and an essential update of the methodology in D2.1.

For Both the Master Harvester Preparation and the Per Organisation Harvester Preparation, the decisions/actions that have to take place can be summarized in the following points:

- Decision on the social media accounts to be tracked: Twitter and Facebook are the first social media sources to be considered due to their proven power in the detection of trends and extraction of insights from crowd wisdom. However, other social media sources can be also considered, while different weights may be imposed for the selected sources depending on the case. Apart from the social media to be used, specific accounts can be also provided, if considered as crucial for the analysis (e.g. influencers)
- Decision on the blogs/Portals of the toy industry to monitor (if any). Although rare in certain manufacturing domains, the existence of dedicated portals, blogs or even wikis should not be overlooked, as it offers targeted information, i.e. less noisy than generic social media platforms, from people that are experts or, at least, interested in the domain. Influential blogposts, vivid discussions and buzz created around a new or existing toy – or even anything that could be afterwards translated into a toy (e.g. animation movie characters) - can act as a first-line trend detection or insights for the approval of a new toy.
- Decision on other text sources for analysis (if any). Other such sources could be feedback forms, since they represent targeted and reliable information and may serve either as validation of existing toy design ideas or as source of needs identification. It is at the discretion of the manufacturer/owner that runs the analysis to integrate such sources or not.

- Selection of key phrases as search terms. Key-phrases/terms should correspond to a toy product, toy category or a new toy design idea in order to support collecting only relevant information from the selected sources for the analysis that follows.
- Decision on the languages of interest. On certain cases, the language of the text (comments, posts, tweets, etc.) to be retrieved may play a significant role according to the nature of the manufacturing company in question, its location etc.

3.2.3.2 *Data Collection – Step 1*

Following the appropriate configurations and decisions of the previous step, this step is responsible for data retrieval and storage, based on the settings of Step 0 where identified search keywords, known user accounts of the domain and preselected blogs are determining the data to be retrieved.

On each specific source there are usually standard approaches for data retrieval. Concerning social media sources, the most popular social media platforms offer APIs that allow 3rd party application developers to access their content, usually for free. Regarding blogs and portals, data retrieval is easily accomplished using configured web crawlers. However, the manufacturer/owner of the analysis needs to decide the time period for data retrieval, in order to reduce to the extent that is possible unnecessary burden from the retrieval of data that are outdated.

3.2.3.3 *Social Analysis and Trends Analysis Preparation – Step 2 (a & b)*

This is an additional step, divided in two sub-steps: Step 2a -Social Analysis Preparation and Step 2b - Trend Analysis Preparation, reflecting the workflow described in the respective section (section 3) of D3.3-ToyLabs Added-Value Components Design and Development-v2.

In this context, in **Step 2a** the settings for the purposes of the specific social feedback analysis to follow are set (i.e. timeframe, sources, language, influencers and specific keywords or hashtags). These settings differ from the ones of the harvesting (Step 0), since they define a subset from the data set collected during Data Collection step, at which the analysis will take place. Apart from these settings, another, new, innovative approach is being added; that of the “Market Set Definition”. According to this approach, the manufacturer is able to define his “universe”, namely his brand and the terms with which anyone may refer to his brand, his products names (and the ways one may refer to his products), his competitors’ brands and his competitors’ products. This “micro-universe” is defined as a market set for the toy manufacturer in question. The manufacturer may define different market sets according to the analysis he wants to implement; namely different competitors and competitive products for each product in question. Thus, each market set represent a different “micro-universe” for the

manufacturer consisting of different set of products, competitors and competitive products that may be saved and fetched appropriately when needed.

In **Step 2b**, the settings for the purposes of the specific trends analysis to follow are set. The points that need to be defined are the same as in Step 2a (i.e. timeframe, sources, language, etc.), but the decisions for them may differ (e.g. different time settings from the social feedback analysis for the trends analysis). Apart from these settings, Trend Analysis Preparation step involves, however, an additional proposition, that of Concept Definition. A concept, in the context of ToyLabs, is a meaningful combination of words (i.e. key-phrases and hashtags) that are of interest (e.g. baby dolls) for the toy manufacturer that performs the analysis. These concepts are then considered as an entity for the methodology that is used in the visualisations of the “Discover actionable insights” step to provide to the user useful and meaningful information customized to his needs and industry’s “language”. The concepts can be saved and retrieved when needed for easier and faster exploration and analysis. Apart from the concepts, parameters for the analysis are also suggested. These are dimensions on which the defined concepts are being analysed and compared among each other. An indicative example could be colours or materials (i.e. the appeal and correlation of each defined colour or material with the defined concepts), but also any other meaningful for the manufacturer parameter can be considered.

3.2.3.4 *Data Pre-processing step – Step 3*

During this step, the diverse input types coming from different social media platforms, blogs, portals etc. are homogenized in some extent. However, due to the diversity of the included sources and the differentiated online discussion patterns, pre-processing of data cannot follow a uniform approach and should thus be appropriately adjusted to the special characteristics of each network/source. As an example, in order to implement feature-level sentiment analysis, processing a blog-post is inherently different from processing a 140-character tweet. Although the latter may contain equally strong and important opinion expressions, its size inevitably reduces its scope, whereas the first may mention multiple toy features and even hold contradictory statements.

Therefore, in this step, social media content is retrieved and in a way normalized, i.e. processed in order to conform to a predefined model. As also described in D2.1, this model will include at least the following information:

- The core textual part of each main piece of data
- The stakeholder, i.e. the opinion holder
- The timestamp of its publishing
- The source of the retrieved data (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)
- The importance indicator, i.e. an additional indicator measuring the text importance and influential power of the given text extracted from source-specific information that will be excluded from the next processing step.

Depending on the source the way this indicator will be measured may vary significantly. In the case of social media sources, an influencer identification algorithm will be applied as a first importance indicator to outline the expected impact of a given piece of information. In the case of blog posts and portals, properties indicating the discussion’s liveliness, such as the length of comments, their number and the discussion growth rate, will define the importance indicator.

As becomes apparent, the aim of this step is to store the diverse data inputs in a coherent way, which may require also certain simple transformations. Furthermore, removal of text considered as noise is envisaged. As an example, depending on the case, promotional marketing content may be considered as such. Removal of malicious content is also envisaged. Furthermore, text sanitisation may be part of this pre-processing step, namely the process of locating and removing sensitive data from a set or database.

3.2.3.5 Data processing step – Step 4

Data processing step is responsible for converting the text that expresses an opinion, an idea, a potential trend, etc. in an appropriate representation for the analysis that will follow in the next steps. Therefore, depending on the type of data and data sources, multiple NLP and machine learning techniques can be employed to determine the features discussed or implied in a given piece of text and transform unstructured text into vectors.

In the course of the previous deliverable, D2.1, several linguistic processing techniques were referenced as part of the approach/methodology proposed, demonstrating the reason behind their proposed usage. These techniques are here briefly referenced in the following table.

Table 3-2 NLP Techniques suggested for ToyLabs

NLP technique	Description
Tokenisation	Tokenisation refers to substituting a sensitive data element with a non-sensitive equivalent, which is referred to as token that has no exploitative meaning or value ⁵ .
Stop-words removal	Stop words usually refer to the most common words in a language, such as “and”, “or” etc.
Repeated character removal	It filters out noise from the examined piece of information (e.g. removal of more than N appearances of the same character).
Special characters	e.g. the use of the @ sign, of hashtags and abbreviations, applying especially in the case of social media.

⁵ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tokenization_\(data_security\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tokenization_(data_security))

removal or replacement	
POS Tagging	It is the process of marking up a word in a corpus as corresponding to a particular part of speech.
Normalisation	It refers to all actions to correct any evident mistakes of the use of a word.
Stemming	Stemming algorithms are algorithms that reduce inflected (or sometimes derived) words to their word stem.
N-gram	N-grams are combined neighbouring words into larger text blocks that support capturing the actual essence of a piece of text.
NER (Named Entity Recognition)	NER is a process for classifying named entities in text into pre-defined categories (e.g. the name of a person or a location), supporting creation of semantically enriched representations.

According to each source case, decision has to be made on the proposed techniques to be applied.

Apart from these linguistic techniques for NLP, other ad-hoc techniques can be also considered, concerning the type of information to store and its structure in order to come up with its best representation in the vector space. Some examples of these techniques could be

- Hashtag extraction or removal: Depending on the methodological needs, hashtags may be desirable and be given specific attention and treated outside the initial text, they may be handled as equivalent information or they may be considered unnecessary and be removed.
- Html elements removal.
- Exclusion of textual inputs that do not meet certain criteria according to the requirements of the methodology. Such examples could be: exclusion of posts with fewer than one predefined number of words, exclusion of posts that use a lot of symbols, exclusion of unlabelled posts (e.g. without hashtags).
- Exclusion of retweets (for Twitter).
- GEO tagging at posts.
- Sorting of posts based on the time of their appearance.

It is worth mentioning that experimentation on real social data of the toy industry case in question may be needed beforehand to decide on the best way to proceed with the Data Processing Step, considering the specific characteristics of the toy industry.

The aim of these techniques is to come up with the features that will serve as vector dimensions to transform the initial text into representative vectors.

3.2.3.6 *Topic & Trend Detection step – Step 5*

Step 5a- Topic Detection step

It is one of the most critical steps of the Market Trends and Social Feedback Methodology and an essential one for both proposed flows, as can be also seen in Figure 3-2.

Topic Detection step can be considered a separate, discrete step of the methodology or it can be considered along with Step 5b – Trend Detection step and be implemented in parallel.

In the case of a separate, discrete approach, two high-level categories of processes have been identified, as also described in D2.1:

- **Topic model algorithms**: used in social media to define the main topic of the examined posts. LDA (Latent Dirichlet Allocation) (Viegas et al. 2006; Wei et al. 2010) is distinguished from the available options to be used for ToyLabs since it can be used uniformly regardless of the data source.
- **Clustering in broader topics/categories**: referring to the grouping of posts/texts/etc. into broader topics in order to detect hidden similarities/correlations among entities. Through this approach, potentially hidden topics can be identified that are associated with specific products and toy categories/entities. Many clustering methods are available, such as keyword clustering or clustering based on co-occurrences.

It needs to be noted, however, that efficient extraction of topics representing toy categories, features and related concepts from informal online user generated content, either directly expressed or implied, heavily depends on the provided domain lexicons and ontologies that guide the topic identification processes.

Step 5b- Trend Detection Step

Trend detection step is only considered as a step in the case of Market Trends Analysis flow. In this case, two different options have been already suggested for ToyLabs, in the context of D2.1, on what concerns the way to run this step, i.e. either to run it in parallel with Step 5a or sequentially, after its conclusion.

The second option (the sequential one) is mostly suggested since it is giving the opportunity to better monitor the corresponding processes and interfere manually when needed. However, it is not binding and it is at the discretion of the responsible person running the analysis to decide on that.

According to the approach proposed for trend detection, two methods are considered:

- **Statistical monitoring of the identified topics over time comparing them with previous periods** that will ensure capturing of the emerging topics

- **Identification of influencers** of a specific domain of interest. It will be used as a weighting strategy that will help toy manufacturers and other interested parties understand how important a particular opinion is. It should be taken into account that the specific characteristic of the domain in question (e.g. animation movies, dolls, etc.) play an important role on the definition of an influencer, since an influencer appearing to have strong influence on a specific community, might constitute a common entity in a different one. It should be also stressed that each social channel asks for different influence observation techniques. As an example, for blogs, the goal is to effectively identify influential bloggers; individuals who are recognised by others, whose activities result in follow-up activities, who have novel perspectives and are eloquent (Keller, Berry 2003). For Twitter, influencers’ definition is more content-oriented, measuring the number of followers, the number of mentions, the number of retweets etc. (Cha et al. 2010).

3.2.3.7 *Sentiment Analysis Step – Step 6*

Sentiment analysis step is the last step of the methodology and a crucial one for both identified flows, as follows:

- In the case of **Social Feedback Analysis Flow**, sentiment analysis provides a social sentiment indicator towards the expressed ideas in social media posts/blogs/etc. as well as an aggregated sentiment for a “topic” representing a product, a brand or anything else which the toy manufacturer in question wants to monitor. These aim to serve as insights on the most warmly received by the public products and the crowd perception about the selected subject.
- In the case of **Market Trends Analysis Flow**, sentiment analysis is an innovative approach, not really met in the standard approaches encountered in the academic literature. In this context, sentiment analysis on top of trending topics will capture approval or disapproval regarding this topics, as well as the intensity of this sentiment, in order to provide the toy manufacturer/designer with insights regarding the decisions that would be most warmly received by potential customers, as well as the ones that would serve as a counter-example informing the manufacturer what he should avoid, enhance and complement existing “ideas” through the wisdom of the crowd and ultimately offer a fresh perspective to the toy design process and the trends worth considering as inspiration for new toy designs.

In the context of the previous deliverable, decisions had been taken on how to proceed with sentiment analysis, i.e. identification and extraction of subjective information and user-generated content from multiple sources in order to determine the emotions that are typically evoked to stakeholders. The updated methodology preserves the decision to apply feature-level, aspect-based sentiment analysis, as well as the guidelines for its extraction from the retrieved documents. According to this

approach, a more fine-grained text analysis is performed, emphasising on the opinion/sentiment target, aiming at giving explicit insights into what the opinion holder liked or disliked instead of attributing a positive or a negative sentiment in a whole language construct (i.e. document, paragraph, sentence or phrase).

The definition for an aspect is something to be determined upon experimentation with true data on the toy industry domain, thus it may vary depending on the case. In the ToyLabs context, the development and testing on the two pilot cases under WP5 has started and is expected to provide an answer on what a meaningful definition for an aspect can be for the toy manufacturers in question. As an example, in the toy industry domain, an aspect, when dealing with a specific product/toy, could be its design, its resistance, its quality, the joy it offers to its users, and anything else that can be identified as a concept discussed by the social media users when referring to this product, which can be also affectively annotated. Furthermore, **it was proposed that unsupervised and semi-supervised approaches are employed, facilitated by visual analytics in order to help the user calibrate the proposed models.** Towards this goal, the creation of context-aware sentiment lexicons based on selected seed words and expanded using rule-based methods, representing experts knowledge regarding patterns on domain discussions, is proposed, controlled through a user-friendly, intuitive interface.

Although not significant updates are witnessed in this step, there are certain points that call for particular attention and need to be further highlighted, as follows:

- More emphasis should be given on the differentiation of the approach when only polarity needs to be identified versus emotions. Emotion represents the way humans understand and interpret sentiment into specific feelings. Section 2.3.1 provided multiple emotion types and justified the need to adopt simpler approaches in toy industry related sentiment analysis tasks. In particular, in ToyLabs, a 4-scale emotion representation (namely Happy, Neutral, Sad, Angry) is proposed. Providing insights into expressed emotions, rather than simplistic polarity indicators calls for more fine-grained sentiment analysis methods that led the decisions for the proposed methodology in this step.
- Sentiment analysis is extremely domain-dependent by nature and also greatly affected by the specific discussion patterns of each social network. Therefore, differentiation of the approaches to use on each case should be considered, as they yield different results at different granularity levels, especially when dealing with social media versus blogs, which have a different rationale and structure.

Furthermore, certain additional propositions are the following:

- Apart from assigning a specific sentiment to the various products and brands that are mentioned or implied, each of the affective words that co-occur with this topics (products, brands, keywords monitored, etc.) will be also extracted,

gathered and made available to the toy manufacturer, possibly offering richer insights into the actual crowd emotions.

- Words that frequently co-occur with toys categories/products mentions but do not belong in predefined categories (products, brands, styles, colors etc.) could serve as inspiration for new toy designs in ways that cannot be thought of and automated in advance. Therefore, a less traditional and restricted keyword extraction method is proposed, leaving space for more inspiration and less automation.

From a technical perspective, all these methods and processes defined above can be implemented in a variety of programming languages, while also having the opportunity to choose among a variety of libraries, toolkits and APIs (e.g. Python’s NLTK and SciPy for natural language processing and machine learning processes).

3.2.3.8 *Conclusion – Discover Actionable insights*

Although not conventionally a step of the ToyLabs Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis Methodology, since it is more of an outcome, it is actually at the center of the proposed approach and even more it drove the methodological decisions taken in the previous described steps. The reason for that is that this “step” is where the actual involvement of the toy manufacturer is considered, i.e. the user of such a methodology and respective component.

Therefore, a lot of discussion had to take place with the ToyLabs pilot partners in order to reach a common understanding on what they would like from such a methodology and system to see and what would be really useful as an insight for them. These iterative discussions served as inspiration and valuable input for the formulation of the above described methodology in order to provide to this step, the Visualisation part, the information needed according to the toy manufacturers’ perspective.

Hence, the opportunity is being given to the system’s user to discover new, previously hidden insights both about trends in the toy industry and their customers’ feeling on their products and brand in order to denature both information into new, innovative, customer-centric toy designs. However, information needs to be “served” at the user through easily digestible visualisations. As an example, generic conclusions about crowd satisfaction or dissatisfaction or indications about general trending topics in the form of plain, unconnected words may be totally non-exploitable by them or “painful” to transform them into useful knowledge.

Sound visual analytics methods will ensure modelling and structuring appropriately the representation of the topics, trends and sentiments inferred, along with information regarding their sources, their location and timing characteristics, the importance level attributed to each one of them and any other available contextual information.

The true value of this phase is to offer a framework for employing visual analytics towards aggregating unstructured ideas and crowd perception and transforming them to design-oriented insights for improved products. Hence, this phase is structured in a way that provides guidelines for the actual adoption of the process, the goals that should be set and the results that can be expected.

D2.1 highlighted the power of visual analytics as well as the value they bring in the current methodology. In the course of this deliverable, indicative visual analytics types to be employed are proposed in the context of enhanced toy design. The scope of the following descriptions is in no way to limit the range of visual analytics, but to provide insights as to how actionable results can be extracted from the collected data, i.e. make their power clearer and their manipulation more intuitive into building a toy design decision support system.

Along the following lines certain indicative propositions are made:

- Correlations among concepts of interest using concept maps: Relations among toy concepts and features, both pre-existing and extrapolated from the grouping steps of Step 5, along with sentiments captured for individual and combined concepts/features, form a rich concept map which can capture previously unknown correlations. Connections revealed during semantic matching and statistical-based grouping (leveraging information coming from toy industry taxonomies and domain-dependent lexical sources) are the enablers for creating links among individual concepts and features. This type applies especially in the case of Market Trends Analysis.
- Sentiment on toy features/concepts of interest (predominant emotion on each toy concept & strength of correlation between concepts) using bubble plots
- Comparison of predominant emotions among brands and toy products using bar charts
- Occurrence of certain search terms across time using time-series charts
- Most frequently occurring terms across all monitored sources using tag clouds
- Sentiment across all: percentage corresponding to each of the 4 emotions for all monitored sources using pie charts

An additional point that needs attention is that of interaction. Although, visual analytics are inherently interactive, certain elements are identified to quantify the interaction mechanisms and ensure that a solution actually falls under the visual analytics paradigm and is not misusing the term to describe data visualizations. Some of these elements are presented here and stressed in order to serve as guidelines on how a ToyLabs user should approach a visual analytics task:

- Gradual and iterative **information filtering** can reveal hidden relations among products and sentiment patterns. Filters should not be limited to predefined

obvious choices, but the user should experiment with turning various fields and field combinations into filters.

- On-the-fly computations, offered in the form of **interactive entity selection**, are an integral part of visual analytics that should be leveraged to gain instant insights into anything that draws the user’s attention.
- Sharing views, visualizations, commented views and visualizations, is an extremely important step of the process, especially for toy manufacturers who, unlike data analysts, are less interested in understanding the process towards pattern mining and more focused on obtaining a valuable and actionable result, regardless of the underlining processes. Hence, collaboration and exchange of created data views is a necessary step, whose value should not be overlooked.

These proposed visual analytics types are expected to be further elaborated and specified under the development activities of the respective component in WP3, as well as through experimentation with the pilots in WP5.

3.2.4 End-user Feedback Acquisition through Augmented Reality

TOYLABS incorporates in the product co-creation process an Augmented Reality approach for acquiring a more complete feedback from childhood experts, market experts, retailers and end-users and related recommendations for improving new product designs.

The Augmented Reality feedback generation methodology takes into full account aspects of personal data protection and privacy of end users profile information, as this is pivotal to ensure trust in the platform and in any feedback generation mechanism in general, unless there is a clear intention of a user to reveal his identity during the feedback authoring. Therefore, the activities to be performed from the user’s side can be categorised as:

- I. Pseudo-Anonymised Feedback by the TOYLABS platform. In this case, feedback is requested by users of the platform (e.g. registered and logged in users) and the platform holds the information about their identity, based on the information they have provided in their profile. However, any information that is passed to the initiator of the feedback (such as the manufacturer) is anonymised and no personal information is disclosed. The advantage of this feedback category over the fully anonymised one is the possibility to provide certain obfuscated statistics about the responders of the questionnaires, which can be linked to the answers as well, but that are not in apposition to link back to the real identity of a user. Thus, questionnaire owners are provided with added value information (such as generalised demographics, etc.) alongside with the basic replies to the questions they pose, allowing them to extract better insights.
- II. Named Feedback. In this case, a user working on a questionnaire agrees to reveal his identity, therefore all feedback is provided to the questionnaire owner together with the profile information of the responder.

In comparison to the 1st version of the approach, it has been decided that providing fully anonymised feedback is not preferable for the purposed of product development. The two categories above are both subject of the selection of the questionnaire creator. Initially, the questionnaire owner can specify which feedback categories of the above he is willing to accept, and in turn the end user can take part in the feedback process only if he agrees to the defined policy. As such, a user is able to refuse to participate in case he does not want to provide any personal information to a “Named” feedback request or agree to participate in case the owner has selected “Pseudo-Anonymised” feedback.

3.2.4.1 Steps

The exact methodological steps to introduce the Augmented Reality module into the overall validation process offered by the TOYLABS platform, as shown in the next figure are:

Figure 3-3 “Augmented Reality as a Feedback channel” deployment methodology

3.2.4.2 Augmented Reality Model Creation/Refinement

This step deals with the uploading of an already designed Augmented Reality model and placeholder in the TOYLABS platform. Considered as the first step of the lifecycle of using Augmented Reality as part of TOYLABS to acquire end user feedback, this step initiates the whole process on the TOYLABS platform and takes as a prerequisite that an Augmented Reality model already exists and is ready to be transferred to the platform. In this context, the platform will provide a designated space that will be used by creators of Augmented Reality models (usually those are the manufacturers or the FabLabs) to upload their designs and describe them, in order to document the information, they would like to display to potential users, besides the Augmented Reality model itself. During this step, the Augmented Reality creator will be in a position to download a simple guide regarding the use of Augmented Reality in TOYLABS, to guide him during the Augmented Reality creation process, pinpointing the supported by the platform formats, specific things that have to be taken under

consideration that regard the model itself, as well as some terms of use that would be automatically accepted upon uploading a model into the platform. Moreover, the guide will also include a description of the features that are available in the platform regarding feedback capturing, so that the Augmented Reality creator would be in a better position to generate his model to make the best out of the feedback collection mechanisms available.

3.2.4.3 *Feedback Mechanisms Selection*

Upon uploading an Augmented Reality model, the manufacturer/FabLabs is then tasked to select out of a simple set of feedback features that will be linked with the model. The aim of this step is to provide to the manufacturer a list of predefined feedback tools (such as comments/posts, small questionnaires, rating buttons) that he could choose to accompany his model with questions that he would like to ask. The tools to be provided should allow both structured and unstructured input by end users (e.g. text as well as selections of predefined answers), and special attention should be given to both select the most appropriate tool, as well as to constrain the number of questions and of the available answers towards easing the user experience (thus long textual questions as well as the expectancy of long answers is something that is strongly advice against).

3.2.4.4 *Feedback Questionnaire Generation*

Step 3 of the whole processes deals with the generation of the content of the questions to be asked to users and to be linked to the feedback mechanism and eventually to the Augmented Reality model. To this end, the questionnaire owner goes on and populates the selected from the previous step tools with questions, providing also the possible answers in case those relate to structured feedback tools.

3.2.4.5 *Presentation and Triggering Method Selection*

Once the selection of the questions is finalised, the questionnaire owner is able to select the presentation triggering method to allow the rendering of the models on the users' devices. For each feedback circle a unique id is being created which shall serve as identifier shared with the users that are invited to provide feedback.

3.2.4.6 *Enhanced Augmented Reality Model Deployment*

This is the pre-final step of the whole process and deals with the actual finalisation of the Augmented Reality feedback setup in the platform and the actual deployment of the model and of the selected feedback tool on the platform. During this step, the platform is populated with all the latest changes and makes public to the addressed users both the Augmented Reality model as well as the accompanying questionnaire.

3.2.4.7 *Feedback Acquisition and Analysis*

This is the last step of the methodology’s cycle and is the actual provision of the feedback to the manufacturer/FabLab and all interested parties. This step relies on the transposition of the answers retrieved through the questionnaires into both long textual descriptions that derive out of the unstructured commented posted by the users on the platform, as well as in simple charts that are able to showcase the preference of the user. During the provision of the feedback, anonymised statistics are provided, in order to guarantee the privacy and the non-exposure of sensitive data of users. However, those anonymised data include certain obfuscated profile information (like country, age group, genders, etc.), that are able to provide enhanced information to manufacturers/FabLabs, without compromising the real identity of users. Furthermore, at this stage, in case end users have agreed to reveal their identities, more detailed information is provided to the manufacturers, such as specific user profiles and demographics, and manufacturers/FabLabs have the option to directly contact users through the platform.

It needs to be noted that before the initial step, the platform will cater for the provision to the Augmented Reality model creator (Toy Manufacturer and FabLab) of a set of instructions to construct and deliver low cost 3D models for Augmented Reality, able to be displayed with the TOYLABS Augmented Reality player.

3.2.4.8 *Augmented Reality Mobile App for Feedback provisioning*

As referred in section 2.4.2, the mobile app to be developed shall be based on ARKit platform provided by Apple, which operates in iOS devices like iPhones and iPad. The following figure represents an indicative flow that a user is supposed to follow in order to provide feedback on a Toy under development:

Figure 3-4 AR mobile app workflow

Finally, a special mention has to be done to the type of the 3d models that the app will be able to support. Given that the app utilizes ARKit engine, all models compatible with the native format that ARKit supports (SceneKit) can be imported and rendered directly. However the scope of the app is to make it easy for any

manufacturer/ toy developer to be able to create and import a model. In order to cover this issue the ToyLabs implementation for the AR app will include a tool for importing all popular 3d file formats, based on the opensource AssimpKit library⁶. The figure below represents the AssimpKit pipeline which will be integrated into the ToyLabs AR Feedback component pipeline.

Figure 3-5 ASSIMPKIT pipeline to be integrated into the ToyLabs AR Feedback component pipeline

This way any 3d model built by all well-known 3d design modelling tools will be seamlessly imported without requiring from the designer to convert it to the SceneKit format, thereby saving an extra step which would probably dishearten ToyLabs users from using the component.

⁶ <http://assimpkit.readthedocs.io>

3.2.5 Partner Matching and Selection Methodology

The Partner Matching and Selection component of the ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-creation Methodology targets to provide the means for identifying and selecting the right stakeholders for a particular project with regard to the creation of a new or improved toy. That given, the respective methodology is structured along two axes:

- *Partner matching*, referring to the identification, definition and classification of the parameters and factors (criteria), required for evaluating the suitability of different candidate partners to undertake certain steps of the ToyLabs Co-creation Methodology.
- *Partner selection*, lying in the specification of the concepts, methods and algorithms, required for making comparisons among candidate partners and selecting the ones that best cover the given requirements.

A quite detailed and comprehensive version of the Partner Matching and Selection Methodology has already been provided within deliverable D2.1, where the ToyLabs Blueprint Model, a model-based approach to manage and inter-link toy, partner, toy co-creation step and technical capabilities' information was developed as a means of facilitating partner matching, and the Analytic Hierarchical Process (AHP), a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) method was chosen to address the problem of partner of partner selection.

From a methodological point of view and as far as the partner matching component is concerned, the ToyLabs Blueprint Model covered most of the requirements, originally brought forward by the project partners, thus leaving limited room for updates and improvements of the respective part of methodology. Such improvements can be found in the directions of:

- Introducing a reputation factor to the Partner, i.e. Partnering Organisation and Partnering Individual blueprints, which can be valued on the basis of proper evidence about each partner's reliability, including an evaluation of their performance in the context of older partnerships by former collaborators.
- Allowing the ToyLabs platform's end users to select themselves the partner matching criteria, based on their company's profile and actual needs, instead of using the whole set of attributes included in the ToyLabs Blueprint Model.
- Introducing the appropriate security and authentication mechanisms, and more specifically applying a framework of graded access, thus allowing additional information disclosure where appropriate and enabling more focused searches based on up-to-date information (fabrication times, experts' availability, etc.).

For the sake of completeness, an overview of the ToyLabs Blueprint Model is provided in the following figure, whereas for more information on its rationale and contents the reader is prompted to deliverable D2.1.

Partner Blueprint		Toy Artefact Blueprint
Partnering Organisation Blueprint	Partnering Individual Blueprint	
Partner Type: <input type="checkbox"/> Manufacturer <input type="checkbox"/> FabLab <input type="checkbox"/> Experts' company	Partner Type: <input type="checkbox"/> Safety Expert <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental Expert <input type="checkbox"/> Childhood Expert <input type="checkbox"/> TSIG Member	Artifact Type: <input type="checkbox"/> Idea/Concept <input type="checkbox"/> Design <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype
Toy Category: <input type="checkbox"/> Dolls & soft-filled toys <input type="checkbox"/> Construction toys and puzzles <input type="checkbox"/> Activity toys	Area of Expertise: <input type="checkbox"/> Safety <input type="checkbox"/> Quality <input type="checkbox"/> Environment <input type="checkbox"/> Children Toys <input type="checkbox"/> Electronics	Toy Category: <input type="checkbox"/> Dolls & soft-filled toys <input type="checkbox"/> Construction toys and puzzles <input type="checkbox"/> Activity toys
Company Contact Information: <input type="checkbox"/> Company Name <input type="checkbox"/> Website/Portal <input type="checkbox"/> E-mail <input type="checkbox"/> Telephone <input type="checkbox"/> Fax <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Address <input type="checkbox"/> Service connection points (end points/URI) <input type="checkbox"/> Contact Person	Expert Contact Information <input type="checkbox"/> Expert Name <input type="checkbox"/> E-mail <input type="checkbox"/> Telephone <input type="checkbox"/> Fax <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Address	ToyLabs Methodology Phase (i.e. Immersion, Design, etc.)
Locations and Facilities: <input type="checkbox"/> Continent <input type="checkbox"/> Country <input type="checkbox"/> Region <input type="checkbox"/> Multiple sites' availability	Location: <input type="checkbox"/> Continent <input type="checkbox"/> Country <input type="checkbox"/> Region	Artifact Version No.
Technical Competencies / Capabilities & Related Equipment Properties:		Technical Requirements
<input type="checkbox"/> 3D Printing <input type="checkbox"/> 3D Scanning <input type="checkbox"/> CAE/FEM & Structural Analysis Simulation <input type="checkbox"/> Circuit Production <input type="checkbox"/> CNC Milling	<input type="checkbox"/> Inkjet Printing <input type="checkbox"/> Knitting Machine <input type="checkbox"/> Laser Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Mould Casting <input type="checkbox"/> Plastic Transformation	
<input type="checkbox"/> Sewing Machine <input type="checkbox"/> Soldering Station <input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Forming <input type="checkbox"/> Vinyl Cutting	Previous Experience	Material Requirements
Certifications Awarded: <input type="checkbox"/> Quality Certifications <input type="checkbox"/> Safety Certifications	Expert Certifications: <input type="checkbox"/> Safety Certifications <input type="checkbox"/> Toy Awards	
Products/Services:	Acting as Representative of: <input type="checkbox"/> Educators/Schools	Time and Cost Requirements

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Types of products produced / services offered o Market o Industry sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Families o End users 	
<p>Qualifications Possessed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Novelty / Innovation (e.g. patents) o Usability o Durability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Accuracy o Productivity o Reputation 	<p>Costs of the Tests</p> <p>Safety & environmental compliance requirements</p>
<p>Economic Criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Man hour Cost o Product Pricelist o Way of Charging 		<p>Customisation Parameters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Text o Look o Style o Other
<p>SLAs undertaken (e.g. terms and conditions, IPR, reward, capacity / availability, etc.)</p>		<p>Related Open Issues</p>
<p>Reputation Factor</p>	<p>Reputation Factor</p>	
<p>Dynamic Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Up-to-date information about current mean fabrication times o Up-to-date information about the experts' availability 	<p>Dynamic Data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Up-to-date information about the experts' availability 	

Figure 3-6. The ToyLabs Blueprint Model

Accordingly, as far as the partner selection component is concerned, potential improvements are identified in the direction of involving the end user in the actual task of weighting the selection criteria, instead of hardwiring the former as a one and out process with which the user cannot intervene.

Attention has to be drawn at this point to the fact that the methodological framework set by the Partner Matching and Selection element of the ToyLabs Open Innovation Model and Co-creation Methodology has been satisfyingly taken into account by Task 3.4 on the implementation and delivery of the respective component, generating the Partner Matching and Negotiation (PMN) module, which allows to

- seek for collaborators based on specific criteria out from a pool of other users;
- get recommendations from the system regarding possible collaborators based on specific thresholds;
- send specific collaboration requests to other users identified through the search results;
- exchange contracts to seal an agreement for collaboration.

Of course, it is the ability to retrieve and process data from different stakeholders that are potential partners, namely business interoperability that may automate and

further enhance the partner matching and selection procedure and the ToyLabs Blueprint Model constitutes a key step towards this direction.

4 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

This deliverable is the outcome of the coordinated effort, in particular its technical partners, NTUA, SLG and AIJU to update the unified methodology that was proposed in D2.1, based on the experience gained by the further research performed, the development of the ToyLabs platform and the feedback on that process and the platform by the pilot partners.

An important conclusion that has been drawn is that at its core, the methodology still stands as valid, although certain parts of it proved to need expansion, refinement and in some cases a course correction. The methodology became less strict and more inclusive of the stakeholders, since it was identified that stakeholders could either have competences that are outside the strict predefined labels of their roles, not having some that would have been expected, or would simply like to expand their operations to include themselves to other parts of the process.

Furthermore, the evolution of the some of the main concepts behind ToyLabs have led to the appreciation of the potential incentive for companies, organisations, and individuals to join the platform, if it is in part seen, not only in its collaboration and innovation potential, but also as a concrete business opportunity. This means that the partner matching methodology has shifted from the solely technical standpoint it was, towards one that, in part, handles the search for a new collaborator as a visit to an aggregated marketplace of competences and reputations. The effort was focused into expanding the added value that ToyLabs has for the process of designing new toys towards some core needs that business have, like finding customers and communication effectively with new partners. These are both reflected in the co-creation and open innovation, and partner-matching methodologies, together with a shift towards the expansion of certain aspects of the platform as tools for business and business process interoperability.

Additionally, the methodological differentiation between market trends analysis and social feedback analysis has, from the extensive testing that was performed, been included, where the results have shown before unforeseen challenges, due to the visual nature of the online activity on these products. In fact, in many toy categories, especially the ones targeting very young children, extensive (and in some case any) textual reviews simply don't exist and products are just shown in photographs as they are. This might make sense, since there is little interest for a parent to read reviews before buying a toy for his child, especially if it's cheap, but there appears to be very little information in the literature on consumer behaviour of parents (or children) regarding the criteria by which toys are selected to be bought. Apart from the influence of catalogues (printed or online), friends, family, hands-on experience, advertisements etc., there has either been no research done on the influence of reviews (online or

offline), or their effect is considered insignificant. Further tests and analyses of data is required to draw definitive conclusions on this matter.

After this revision of the integrated methodology of ToyLabs, the resulting modifications will be incorporated into the refined design and development of the ToyLabs added-value components for WP3 to reflect the revised understanding of the ToyLabs specific methodological and scientific goals.

ANNEX I: REFERENCES

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